

EXPERIENCES OF OUT-OF-FIELD TEACHERS TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

This study is a qualitative research using hermeneutic phenomenological design, aimed to understand the lived experiences of non-English teachers teaching English subjects in the Schools Division of Baybay City and proposed program/platform that can aid them. The study used purposive sampling technique in choosing the participants. There were different inclusion and exclusion criteria determined in the study to ensure that all of the participants experience out-of-field teaching phenomenon in teaching English subjects. The study utilized semi-structured interview with open-ended question, interview schedules, written documentation, direct observation using note-taking and video recording. The data were analyzed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis to better present the realities of out-of-field teaching. Based from the results of the study there were five themes that emerged, these were Hurdles of a Hero, Fish Out of Water, Against the Current, Echoes of Voices, Compass into the Woods and Double-edged Sword. Hurdles of A Hero has three sub-themes, which are Difficulty in Difference, Peeling the Shell and Struggles in Scaffolding. Fish Out of Water has three sub-themes which are Against the Current, Sailing Journey and Extra Hat. Moreover, Echoes of Voices this theme has two sub-themes, which are Echoes of Emergence and Common-Uncommon. In addition, Compass into the Woods has two sub-themes which are Aid of Maneuver and Sharpening of Arrows. Lastly, Double-edged Sword has three sub-themes which are Mask of Unsureness, Self in Someone's Shoes and Reflective Mirror. The study interpreted the different lived experiences of non-English teachers. These lived experiences expressed by the teachers revealed the different learnings and the challenges non-English teachers met while teaching English subjects. Thus, teaching English subjects out-of-field was beneficial for other teachers yet challenging to some. However, their lived experiences become their additional teaching experience that help them cultivate themselves and contribute to their own meaning of the teaching profession.

Keywords: *Out-of-Field Teaching, Lived Experiences, Non-English Teachers*

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INTRODUCTION

Teaching is an essential component in developing young minds towards learning and development (Lagria, 2021). Hence, as for Tingzon and Buyok (2022) teachers play vital roles in building the highest potential among learners, developing necessary skills for them to adapt to the changing demands of the society and improving their knowledge in responding to the needs of this modern world. Thus, for teachers to be able to help their learners they must be knowledgeable or expert in the subjects that they are teaching. Furthermore, as for Roxas (2022) it is argued that teachers must show expertise in the subjects they are teaching. However, in reality these expert teachers are sometimes not teaching their area of expertise which is known as out-of-field teaching.

Moreover, as defined by Pacaña et al. (2019) out-of-field teaching is teaching of any field outside of the teacher's area of specialization. Recently, based on the study conducted by Van Overschelde & Piatt (2020) out-of-field teaching is not a characteristic of the teacher, but a depiction of the misalignment of teacher's qualifications and a class subject being taught. Hence, in the Philippines as for Rebucas (2022) teaching outside specialized topics offer extensive difficulties and teachers show concern in managing their present circumstance. Thus, much research has examined the out-of-field phenomenon, there are different conclusions and ways on how to overcome and provide aid to this matter. However, these studies are focused on the different aspects of out-of-field phenomenon such as causes, ways to overcome and so much more. Moreover, less attention is given to the lived experiences of Non-English majors teaching English subjects.

In addition, according to Lagria (2021) the lack of competent teachers to teach English courses posit a big problem when it comes to learners' acquisition of appropriate, precise knowledge and understanding. With having less published works focused on the lived experiences of non-English teachers teaching English subjects, this becomes the drive of this research. Providing voices and amplifying it and proposed program/platform to aid them is the focus of this research. Furthermore, having information on the lived experiences of Non-English teachers can unfold new information about it and motivate other researchers to conduct studies that are beneficial to teachers.

METHODOLOGY

This research made use hermeneutic phenomenology in understanding the lived experience of non-English majors teaching English subjects. This study specifically utilized the Heideggerean hermeneutics. According to Bryne (1998) Heideggerean hermeneutics as research methodology assumes meaning making is embedded in the process of dialogue between the interpreter and the narrator. He further added that Heidegger introduced the concept of hermeneutic circle, which is a way of articulating and interpreting discourse. The setting of this research was at the Schools Division of Baybay City, which is in Region VIII, Baybay City, Leyte. This hermeneutic phenomenological research participants were the different Junior and Senior High Schools of the Schools Division of Baybay City. This research used purposive sampling technique. There were 12 teachers who were the participants in the study coming from the different schools in the Schools Division of Baybay City.

The following were the inclusion criteria of the study. First, Participants must be 22 years old or above during the conduct of the study. Second, participants had worked as a teacher for at least one year. Third, participants must experience out-of-field teaching phenomenon first-hand. Fourth, participants must have been teaching English subject/s despite not being able to study it during college or university years. Lastly, teaching station of the prospective participants must also be under the Schools Division of Baybay City and consented to be part of the study. The different exclusion criteria of the study were as followed. First, participants who are teaching below one (1) year or newly hired teachers. Second, participants who were no longer experiencing out-of-field teaching. Third, participants who did not sign the consent form to be included since this research is voluntary and in free will. These pre-established criteria made other participants excluded in the study for this research to be reliable.

There were different instruments that were utilized during the conduct of this study in order to gather the data from the participants. These were face-to-face interview using open-ended questions and interview schedules, field notes and video recording to capture better the participants' lived experience. There were different stages abided in data collection process; these were Preliminary Activities, Main Activities and Post Activities. In this study, Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis was used. Alase (2017) stated IPA allows for multiple participants who experience similar events to tell their stories without any distortions and/or prosecutions. Hence, the steps in analyzing the data on out-of-field teaching in English subjects of this study followed the different steps as identified by Smith and Osborn (2007).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EXPERIENCES OF OUT-OF-FIELD TEACHERS TEACHING ENGLISH SUBJECTS

HURDLES OF A HERO

This is the first theme, which has three themes; these are Difficulty in Difference, Peeling the Shell and Struggles in Scaffolding. Teachers have always been associated with the word hero. Teachers' sacrifices to their learners such as their time, resources and the drive to change their learners' lives are more than enough to call them heroes. They had always been celebrated and learners look up to them as their real-life hero. However, just like the usual heroes we have seen and idolized in cinema screen or in television, our teachers are facing different hurdles in their teaching profession. Hurdles signify the different obstacles that teachers in the out-of-field phenomenon are facing. They are dealing these obstacles in an everyday teaching discussion and interaction to their learners in the out-of-field teaching in English subjects.

Difficulty in Difference

Difficulty means hardship meet by someone along their journey that requires great efforts to overcome. Thus, this is used in the study as a representation for the phenomenon out-of-field teaching, which is not in line with these teachers' degree that they had graduated. This difficulty in difference reveals out-of-field teachers' English subjects' struggles while teaching. Moreover, based on the lived experiences of these out-of-field teachers they find teaching English subjects as an obstacle or a difficult situation that they face in their teaching profession.

Based on their lived experiences teaching English subjects is different to the course or bachelor's degree that they had graduated that made it difficult for them since it requires them to do more research about it to support their discussions. The command over the language is one of the difficulties meet by some. What to discuss or what to focus in their discussion is also a difficult situation they are dealing with, especially English grammar or literature. They further compared teaching on their field, which they have more 'stock knowledge' or foundation to its basics unlike to the teaching of English subjects.

This is also confirmed in the study of Magdaraog and Benavides (2020) that out-of-field teachers have difficulty in lesson planning. Therefore, calibrating themselves like buying books and surfing the internet before facing their learners are their ways of combatting this phenomenon. However, this becomes one of their difficulty. As for Augusto (2019) he conveys that out-of-field teachers have dealt with different difficulties in their task that made it tiring.

Peeling the Shell

This sub-theme is a metaphor that stands for the act of peeling the shell only but not able to set inside of it. This is a representation of teachers touching the surface only in their discussions in English subjects despite great efforts and lengths to impart deeper understanding to their learners yet still end up with shallow discussions.

The Peeling the Shell interprets that out-of-field teachers teaching English subjects were not able to sub-task their lessons or the competency into smaller components for their learners to have in-depth understanding. According to Cahapay (2020) curriculum unpacking does not form a process of classroom instruction however, researchers claim that it has a potent influence on the learning outcomes as a result of the classroom instruction.

Hence, there are instances that the teacher did not understand the lesson resulting to just plainly dictating the information instead of providing deeper discussions. This is in conformity to the study of Rebucas and Dizon (2020) wherein there is a challenge in the mastery of the lesson when it comes to out-of-field teaching. Subject integration also is difficult for the participants. Thus, these can be resolved if English teachers are the one teaching English subjects. This is agreed by Roxas (2022) that misaligned or out-of-field teachers should be placed in their proper assignments ideally to their unique, specialized subjects.

Struggles in Scaffolding

The struggles are result of not able to achieve something easily. Scaffolding is used to support people who are working to build or create infrastructure. The main aim of scaffolding is to provide aid to people in accomplishing certain tasks. In education, scaffolding is used to provide assistance and aid learners to have deeper understanding on the different competencies. Scaffolding in simpler term is any activity done before or after the giving of the lesson to fully support learners build concrete understanding on it. Thus, Struggles in Scaffolding represent teachers' struggles in providing support or activities to their learners.

The out-of-field teachers teaching English subjects are struggling to provide learners with activities suitable for their differentiated learning needs and in contextualizing activities. Contextualizing activities is highly encouraged in order for the learners to relate and understand the lessons based on their own reality. Providing activities is a struggle since they do not have prepared or planned activities unlike to their own area of specialization. This is in consonance to

Lagria (2021) that out-of-field teachers experienced difficulty in selecting the best-fitted activity for their learners. Seshea (2017) conveys and supports the findings that out-of-field teachers feel inadequately prepared to teach. According to Arendain and Limpot (2022) research has shown that teachers who teach non-specialized subject find it difficult to use appropriate teaching strategies.

FISH OUT OF WATER

This theme personified the teachers as fish who are in a completely different environment. Hence, out of water signifies the out-of-field teaching experiences of teachers, which are completely different from the course or area of specialization they were trained to do for many years. Just like the fish out of water, teachers are struggling to be acquainted with the foreign surrounding that they are facing. This theme reveals the different adjustments that teachers are willing to undertake to give their best in teaching and continuously offer quality education to their learners.

Against the Current

Against is a word, which means opposite of something or not innate to someone and the current is a movement of water that is only in one direction, which is a metaphor for teachers who are teaching English subjects out-of-field. Based from their experiences going against the current requires a lot of effort to accomplish since this requires for one to overcome.

The shared experiences of participants revealed that they are having hard time relating themselves to the topics that they are discussing. This relatedness is quite hard to achieve for the participants especially in deepening lessons in English like grammar, which made them feel that teaching English subjects is a misplacement to them. The absence of knowledge on relatedness with the topics may cause boredom to the learners. Moreover, planning as seen as one of the essential aspect in the delivery of lesson is also not observed since participants cannot

visualize or create their own plan when they view the competencies in English subjects. Hence, organizing the lessons is also a challenge for the participants since the participants cannot connect themselves with the concepts in English.

The participants are confused on what lessons to touch or discuss because they are unable to relate. Rebutas (2022) argues that one of the challenges of out-of-field teachers is the familiarization of the subject. According to him out-of-field teachers experienced struggle in delivering and discussing lessons or even answering learners misconception due to the reason that they are not familiar with the subject and the subject itself does not relate to their field of specialization.

Sailing Journey

Sailing is done at sea by the sailors or anglers. They harness the power of the wind serving as the engine of the sailing boat. This is done by slowly adjusting as to where the wind happens to blow instead of going against it. This requires abilities like alertness and flexibility to take full

control of the sailing journey. The theme is a representation as to what are the different things teachers must go through in order to teach English effectively being out-of-field.

Based from the sharing there is an adjustment to participants' ways of teaching. Teaching English subjects is like becoming a jack-of-all-trades but a master of none. The feeling of the participants being uncomfortable in out-of-field teaching is slowly turning to an act of adaptation at the end. As for the insight of Bayani and Guhao (2018) teachers have a calling to be flexible and versatile in order to teach the subject well.

Hence, the years of experience provide ample time for the participants to adjust and polish their skills. This theme interprets that as a teacher teaches repeatedly in the same out-of-field subjects in English they become better as the years go by. Their experiences and learners' interaction through the years provided them time to adjust their teaching style. This is supported by Arendain and Limpot (2022) that out-of-field teaching give additional knowledge. Based on their study teachers who teach a subject they have not mastered gain more knowledge most especially in the subject they teach.

Extra Hat

Extra in its simplest definition means additional. Moreover, hat is an object used to cover the head for protection. Hence, hat in this study means roles portrayed or responsibilities assigned to a person. Teaching is undeniably one of the most demanding profession of all the professions and this is also considered as the noblest profession among all. Teachers have great influence to learners, community and in the society. Thus, teachers are facing many responsibilities in the call of this noble profession.

Based from the sharing, teaching English demands more time and resources as this is out of their field of specialization. They expressed the exhaustion faced especially in planning

their lessons and viewed phenomenon as an additional burden. This conforms to the study of Rebutas and Dizon (2020) that too much lesson preparation is an additional burden on the part of the teachers. They explicate that teachers teaching outside their specialized topic confronted difficulties in readiness of the lesson and during the time spent instructing.

Participants also spent more in buying resources suitable to their learners. Hence, this theme also is an interpretation of the different investments that they need to do in order to teach better. This relates with the findings of Lagria (2021) that one of the challenges encountered by out-of-field teaching is time and financial constraint. The study reveals that out-of-field teachers need to manage their work time and equipping themselves with enough knowledge at their own cost. This is congruence with the statement of Aventura and Viña (2023) that out-of-field teaching is an exhausting job.

ECHOES OF VOICES

Echoes are sounds produced by a voice that are usually reflected or heard at back by the speaker. This theme reveals different voices from the phenomenon out-of-field teaching.

Echoes of Emergence

This is the first sub-theme where emergence is the act of appearing into or developing. Thus, emergence is used in the study to represent acceptance and embracement on how the out-of-field teachers teaching English accept and live with what they are currently facing. Based from the sharing of the lived experiences of the participants these show how the participants are accepting their current situation as out-of-field teachers. This supports that result of the study of Aventura and Viña (2023) that teachers realized that out-of-field teaching is not all about burdens and hardships but somehow they have also gained new learnings.

Teachers shared that this is a challenge in order to grow professionally and explore other fields because instead of settling to the comfort of what they are already familiar with, out-of-field teaching can contribute to their personal growth. However, participants strongly emphasized the different benefits for the learners to have teachers who teach with their specialization. Bayani and Guhao (2018) agree with this that proper teacher placement is essential. Out-of-field teachers in their study convey that in order not to compromise learners learning and teacher's welfare alignment must be prioritized by the school. Moreover, out-of-field teachers based on their lived experiences also expressed that teachers could learn if they just put their mind on learning unfamiliar concepts.

Common-Uncommon

This represents the echoes of out-of-field teaching in the past that is still heard up to the present time. Common represent the things that are usual and known by the majority of the people. While, uncommon is the complete opposite of it wherein it is considered unusual, extraordinary or rare. These Common-Uncommon pair of words is considered an oxymoron

wherein two opposing words or ideas are paired to form a phrase. These two contradictory words is used in the study to represent existence of out-of-field teaching which can be considered as usual despite of it being unusual.

Based from the sharing, they are already knowledgeable to the situation that they might face once they are hired. Some of the participants were informed already with the out-of-field teaching phenomenon through the experiences of other teachers who are close to them and they perceive out-of-field teaching as ‘normal’ due to some teachers especially in Senior High School who experienced and it is like a tradition. Hence, others convey that out-of-field teaching is like helping each other especially the specialized teacher to lessen their subject loads.

This theme interprets basing on the lived experiences of the participants that out-of-field teaching is common and existed even in the past despite of being uncommon or unusual since teachers are teaching different subjects that they are not trained to do. As for Du Plessis et al. (2023) out-of-field teaching is common in education systems worldwide.

COMPASS INTO THE WOODS

Compass into Woods is a metaphor on teacher’s skills, ways and their strategies in addressing challenges. A compass is a small circular instrument used by travelers or people looking for directions to be in their desired destination or place. This serves as a guide for people to navigate properly the unknown route. Compass Into the woods represents the idea of uncertainty of teachers teaching out-of-field.

Aid of Maneuver

Aid as per definition is anything that provides assistance or help to someone in need while Maneuver represents movement into specific direction that requires undeniable skill to operate. This theme is a metaphor on the different strategies created and developed by the teachers who are in the out-of-field teaching in English subjects. Based from the sharing, their main way of assisting themselves is research through internet and utilizing its different search engines. Roxas (2022) expressed agreement with this as he conveyed that in teaching subjects outside of one’s area of expertise, technological integration and hands-on exploration of ICT tools appeared more beneficial.

Using learning materials or resources developed during the modular-distance learning like self-learning modules and DepEd TV/DepEd develop learning videos that undeniably supported the participants. The localized Learner’s Activity Sheet (LAS) or Simplified Learning Materials (SLMs) were considered aid of maneuver. As argued by Morato (2020) learning modules are carefully crafted and created inside a content area that depends on the understanding of the first concept in order to understand the second. It at all cost should improve the standard of learning for learners as they face the struggles and challenges of the learning process.

Establishing consultation with English majors in schools where participants seek for support from their colleagues who are English majors through asking questions or by verifying that their understanding of specific English concepts were correct is a great help. This is in congruence with the result of the study of Arendain and Limpot (2022) that no one is in monopoly of knowledge. They further convey that teachers teaching subjects they have not mastered should make a means to overcome the challenges they face through seeking help from their fellow teachers who are knowledgeable in a specific subject. Furthermore, colleagues' motivation helped them. This is also confirmed by Magdaraog and Benavides (2020) on their conclusion that consultation with the experienced colleague in the school emerged as the common coping mechanism developed by the out-of-field teachers in order to overcome the difficulty.

Sharpening of Arrows

Arrows is considered as one of the earliest developed tools; this can be used in varied purposes like hunting or even as a type of sport. Thus, sharpening is an act of polishing or making and retaining the sharpness of an object. Sharpening of Arrows is used in the study as metaphor to show the idea of assisting out-of-field teachers in teaching English subjects but need further polishing and guidance.

Based from the sharing intensive training and workshop intended for them can gain teaching techniques that are useful in teaching English subjects, which can be done during In-Service Training (INSET). Augusto (2019) supports this result as he claims that training must be given to the out-of-field teachers to boost their confidence and to avoid job dissatisfaction. Letting English teachers or teachers who specialized in English as resource speakers or trainers to those out-of-field teachers will surely help them gather teaching strategies and techniques needed to discuss better the concepts or lessons in English subjects.

This is in accordance with the suggestion of Magdaraog and Benavides (2020) that subject coordinators may serve as learning facilitators who are knowledgeable to the phenomenon and its implications. The coordinators who are aware of the needs of out-of-field teachers should experience support programs. Toring (2017) argues that out-of-field teachers must be provided with regular trainings. He further claims that trainings should not just focus on the contents of the out-of-field teaching assignments but also to its teaching approaches. Mentoring and teaching schemes for these out-of-field teachers in their schools must be strengthened and strictly observed.

DOUBLE-EDGED SWORD

This is the last theme of the study. This kind of sword is sharp in both edges it can help or be in opposite depending on the person using it. This Double-edged Sword is a metaphor to the positive and the negative effects of out-of-field teaching to the participants.

Mask of Unsureness

Mask of Unsureness is the first sub-theme. Mask is made of any materials like papers or plastics which are used to cover the face of a person. This is done for different purposes like for celebrations such as festival or just to plainly hide the face of a person. Unsureness in simplest word means doubt. This reflects teachers wearing mask of self-doubt within themselves as out-of-field teachers in English subjects.

Based from the lived experiences of the participants teachers develop self-doubt or being unsure along their journey as out-of-field teachers to teach English subjects. They lost their self-confidence due to the idea of what they can give is limited and there were times that they were unsure of their discussions based on their lived experiences. Confidence then is very important. This is validated by Pacaña et al. (2019) that out-of-field teaching trigger incompetence and lack of self-confidence. Based on their study out-of-field teachers were under much pressure when their learners questioned and they could not satisfy them because of the lack of in-depth knowledge. Rebucas and Dizon (2020) are in consonance with this that out-of-field teachers make themselves doubtful on sharing information and ideas because they have not mastered the lessons.

Self-doubt is also evident based on the participants thinking if other teachers are present during their class discussions, what if their colleague might say something or criticize them for it. Thus, the lived experiences of the participants guaranteed the interpretation of the study that resulted to the emergence or sub-theme Mask of Unsureness. The feeling of being nervous or afraid if their learners will ask questions which they do not have answers or knowledge to it at that moment is reflected from the participants lived experiences. They develop the feeling of anxiousness as they discuss their lessons in front of their class. Cinkir and Kurum (2015) confirmed this that the participants of their study believed that out-of-field teachers were stressful, anxious, hopeless, and disappointed and suffered from burnout.

Self in Someone's Shoes

Putting self in someone's shoes is an idiomatic expression, which means thinking of other people. This self in someone's Shoes represents how teachers are being emphatic to their learners. Based from the sharing, participants tend to pity their learners that they are the one teaching English subjects. They think of the knowledge learners can get if the teachers teaching the said subjects are those who specialized or major it. There is a feeling of being ashamed of their learners. The thought that learners might provide silent criticisms to the participants leads to this feeling of being ashamed. It is important for teachers to feel pride or self-esteem of what they are doing.

As for Erözkan et al. (2016) there was a positive relationship between self-esteem and self-efficacy on the individual's happiness. According to Mbuva (2019) studies show that self-esteem is integral of the growth of both teachers and learners who interact in varied capacity daily. He further conveys that if teachers have distorted image of themselves it is possible that they become incapacitated in their teaching career. This self in someone's shoes is evident as participants think of the best for their learners instead of themselves. Participants put their learners ahead of them as they try hard to deliver quality education despite being in the out-of-field teaching. Thus, teachers are like parents for they always put their learners ahead of them.

Reflective Mirror

This Reflective Mirror refers to the reflection of a person when they see themselves in the mirror. Likewise, this definition applies in this theme to better view out-of-field teachers' realizations based on their reflected lived experiences. Based from the sharing, out-of-field teachers in English subjects provide suggestions to teachers who might experience the same journey that they had been through due to this phenomenon.

They suggest that future teachers and potential teachers should not just focus on their own field and should try to develop their skills in other subjects such as English to prepare them if they will be asked to teach out-of-field subjects in the near future. Preparing oneself reflects one's desire for professional growth. As for Scheeler et al. (2016) pre-service educators must be prepared to enter the field of teaching armed with an empirically supported knowledge base, fully sufficient opportunities to practice and to master selected teaching practices, and the professional wisdom to adapt the instructional environment to meet individual needs of the learners.

The value of eagerness to learn, should be adaptable, flexible and open for learning. Teaching out-of-field subjects can develop skills on that subject along with one's area of specialization. They should also possess patience along in their journey paired with hard work to become an effective teacher despite being in out-of-field teaching phenomenon. According to social constructivist theory of Vygotsky (1978) this supported the belief that the merging of perceptual and humanistic qualities in teaching lead to teaching effectiveness as cited by Ibad (2018). Based on their lived experiences this out-of-field teaching also promotes holistic growth to teachers. Hence, this theme interprets that teachers and future teachers must be innovative, strategic and hardworking. The different realizations of teachers as they journey in the out-of-field teaching became their reflection just like as they view themselves in the mirror. This reflection can lead to their growth and widen their definitions to the teaching profession.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The result of this study concludes that the experiences of the participants are vital aspects in their teaching career that changed or widened their view to teaching profession as a whole and made them a better teacher. Support from peers is a motivating factor. Furthermore, attending trainings, programs and symposiums help harness their potential skills. Teachers can be trained by highly proficient teachers or those teachers who are major in English in their respective stations without spending large amount of resources.

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